

Organically modified superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ – Synthesis, characterization, absorption and photoluminescence behaviour

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Abstract : Synthesis of superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ with complex morphologies under the influence of lauric acid in methanol medium was investigated. Lauric acid directed the transformation of thermodynamically stable broken sponge-like calcite CaCO_3 to ellipsoid-like vaterite. Further, flower shaped amorphous $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ resulted after doping the lanthanide elements to CaCO_3 . The morphology, composition and phases of the synthesized compounds was characterized with scanning electron microscopy (SEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA). Water contact angle of 140° indicates superhydrophobic behavior of lauric acid modified CaCO_3 . More importantly, these materials also displayed high absorption for oils, dyes and genotoxic solvents such as xylene and toluene. The room temperature photoluminescence (PL) measurements of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ showed emission at 484 nm (blue) and 545 nm (green), respectively.

Keywords : Carbonates, lauric acid, morphology, superhydrophobicity, photoluminescence.

Introduction

Calcium carbonate has been extensively studied as model biomineral which exists in three crystalline forms such as calcite, aragonite and vaterite^{1,2}. Calcium carbonate finds wide variety of applications in industry, environmental remediation and synthesis of metal oxides³. Control of crystal growth via bio-inspired route is an attractive approach for production of complex mineral morphologies with novel properties^{1,4,5}. It is well known that organic additives with carboxylic acid functional groups can direct the phase and morphology of calcium carbonate⁶⁻⁹. Shape controlled synthesis of composite inorganic materials, with inorganic-organic interface, is an emerging soft chemical approach. Surface of inorganic crystals are often modified by a variety of fatty acids through chemisorption for various technological applications¹⁰⁻¹². Adsorption of hydrophobic solvents is one of them. Many studies have shown that the surface coated hydrophobic metal carbonates also exhibit the property of removing oils and coloured dyes¹³⁻¹⁶.

Photoluminescence is an important optical phenom-

enon which involve absorption of energy and subsequent emission of light. Emission of high quality colour luminescence is an attractive feature of lanthanide elements doped into host lattices¹⁷. In general, metal oxides, phosphates, vanadates and silicates act as conventional host lattices for rare-earth elements¹⁸. Recently CaCO_3 also used as host material for lanthanide elements, Tb^{3+} and Eu^{3+} , for making inorganic phosphors¹⁹. In addition to luminescence behaviour, lanthanide elements play an important role as a dopant in stabilizing the phases and morphology of calcium carbonate^{20,21}.

In this study, production of superhydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ in presence of lauric acid was investigated. In particular, the influence of lauric acid and lanthanide dopants on morphology, absorption and luminescent properties were explored.

Results and discussion

Morphology and phase identification :

The influence of lauric acid at variable concentrations (mole ratio $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{LA}] = 100, 50, 10$) on phase and

morphology of CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ was examined. Fig. 1 shows the formation of CaCO_3 calcite phase with broken sponge-like morphology in control experiments i.e. without addition of crystal growth modifier, lauric acid. Trace amount of vaterite phase was also observed along with the major phase of calcite. In presence of lauric acid, this broken sponge-like calcite (2–4 μm size) transformed to ellipsoid-like vaterite phase composed of nanocrystallites (Fig. 1b). After 24 h of growth, ellipsoid like microspheres of size 800 nm–1 μm appeared at low molar ratio of $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{LA}] : 100$. The size was found to have decreased to 600–900 nm on increasing the molar ratio of $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{LA}]$ to 10. Growth of calcium carbonate was carefully examined at different time intervals at mole ratio of $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]/[\text{LA}] : 10$. Crystals were isolated after 6 h, 12 h, 24 h, and examined through SEM. Calcium carbonate nanospheres of size 40–80 nm,

Fig. 1. SEM images of CaCO_3 produced in (a) control experiments, (b) presence of lauric acid (mole ratios $[\text{M}]/[\text{L}] = 100$).

sub-micron spheres of 100–150 nm and 600–900 nm appeared after 6 h, 12 h and 24 h of growth, respectively (Fig. 2). As shown in Fig. 3, amorphous flower shaped morphology of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ resulted after doping the rare-earth elements into CaCO_3 in presence of lauric acid at molar ratio of $[\text{Ln}^{3+}]/[\text{LA}] : 10$. Existence of La^{3+} and Tb^{3+} in CaCO_3 was evident by EDAX spectrum (Fig. 3b, 3d).

Powder X-ray diffraction patterns at 22.65, 29.08, 35.60, 38.95, 42.80, 47.10, 48.07, 57.08 (calcite) and 24.48, 32.47, 38.24, 44.62, 49.59, 56.17 (vaterite) confirmed the calcium carbonate phases produced under different experimental conditions (Fig. 4a, 4b). Non-crystalline powder patterns of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ are shown in Fig. 4c, 4d.

Fig. 2. SEM images of CaCO_3 growth in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios $[\text{M}]/[\text{L}] = 10$) at (a) 6 h, (b) 12 h, (c) 24 h, (d) enlarged picture of 24 h growth.

Fig. 3. SEM images of metal carbonates produced in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios $[\text{M}]/[\text{L}] = 10$); (a) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, (b) EDAX spectrum of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, (c) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, (d) EDAX spectrum of $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$.

Fig. 5 shows IR spectra of the hydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ synthesized using lau-

Fig. 4. Powder XRD patterns of CaCO_3 produced in control experiments; (a) CaCO_3 , (b) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, (c) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$, (d) produced in presence of lauric acid (mole ratios $[\text{M}]/[\text{L}]=10$) (c = calcite, v = vaterite).

ric acid. The characteristic peaks at 2512, 1416, 874, 745 cm^{-1} in the spectrum are attributed to the vaterite phase of CaCO_3 . The peaks close to 2924 and 2852 cm^{-1} indicate the presence of lauric acid on the surface of carbonates (Fig. 5a, 5b, 5d). Additionally, the peak observed at 1082 cm^{-1} in the spectra of above mentioned compounds is assigned to the Ca-O bond of calcium laurate^{13,22}. The above data was compared with calcium carbonate produced in control experiments (Fig. 5c).

Fig. 5. FT-IR spectra of (a) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$, (b) CaCO_3 and (d) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ produced in the presence of lauric acid; (c) CaCO_3 produced in control experiments.

TGA analysis revealed that the CaCO_3 prepared using lauric acid contained a thin layer of both calcium laurate and lauric acid around the particles. Fig. 6a, shows the

% weight loss of CaCO_3 prepared with and without lauric acid, indicating that CaCO_3 (calcite phase) prepared without lauric acid in control experiments was stable up to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and decomposed to CaO and CO_2 by losing 44% of weight (Initial sample weight is 7.572 mg). The CaCO_3 synthesized in presence of lauric acid (Fig. 6b) exhibited a weight loss of 27% at a temperature below 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. This weight loss may possibly be attributed to the decomposition of lauric acid and calcium laurate. The same is confirmed by FT-IR peaks at 2924, 2852, 1082 cm^{-1} . Vaterite phase of calcium carbonate decomposed to CaO and CO_2 in the region 300 to 600 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Initial sample weight is 10.347 mg).

Fig. 6. TGA spectrum of CaCO_3 produced in (a) control and (b) presence of lauric acid.

Superhydrophobic nature :

The hydrophobic nature of organically modified CaCO_3 was investigated through water contact angle measurement. Change in the surface characteristics of CaCO_3 after modification with lauric acid was done by sessile drop method using Phoenix, SEO, Korea. The prepared sample was pressed into a thin uniform layer on to a double sided adhesive tape stuck to a glass plate. As per earlier reports, contact angles of 103 $^{\circ}$, 122 $^{\circ}$ and 91–140 $^{\circ}$ have been reported for CaCO_3 treated with stearic acid²², oleic acid²³ and lauric acid¹³, respectively. It has been reported that the most important factor in determining the oleophobic properties of films of fatty acids, and similar polar organic compounds, adsorbed on solid surfaces was the density of the adsorbed molecules on the

surfaces²⁴. In the present investigation, the value of water contact angle at 140°, as shown in Fig. 7, suggests superhydrophobic nature of CaCO₃ modified with lauric acid. The plausible explanation put forth for this behaviour is that during the growth of the material, COOH groups of lauric acid are directed towards Ca²⁺ ions whereas the long chain alkyl groups direct away resulting in hydrophobic behaviour.

Fig. 7. Water contact angle of hydrophobic CaCO₃.

Absorption properties :

Absorption of oil and genotoxic solvents by CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ was investigated according to Sarkar *et al.*¹³ (Fig. 8). Sunflower oil was selected to test the absorption properties of above metal carbonates. PTCDA was added to the oil to impart red colour (Fig. 8a). The absorption of xylene and toluene by synthesized carbonates was also investigated. The ratio of organic solvent to water was fixed at 1 : 10 wt% to measure the absorption efficiency. The synthesized CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ exhibited 100, 69.2 and 35.2% oil absorbing efficiency, respectively. Furthermore, these materials also displayed selective absorption of xylene and toluene. CaCO₃ showed 70.5 and 79.9% absorption efficiency for xylene and toluene, respectively. CaCO₃ : La³⁺ absorb 21.0 and 23.5% of xylene and toluene, respectively. Similarly CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ exhibited 50.0% and 56.0% absorption efficiency for xylene and toluene, respectively. Relatively CaCO₃ displayed better absorption efficiency as compared to mixed metal carbonates. This may be explained on the basis of hydropho-

Fig. 8. Absorption of oil (a) dispersion of PTCDA-dye in oil layer, (b and c) absorption of oil by CaCO₃.

bic behaviour of lauric acid coated CaCO₃ in which the long chain alkyl groups direct away from Ca²⁺ ions towards non-polar substrate like oil and genotoxic solvents, thereby resulting in removal of the same. The data is presented in Table 1.

Photoluminescence :

Luminescence property of lanthanide carbonates was also investigated. The La³⁺ ions with unfilled 4f orbitals in lanthanide carbonates do not possess luminescence. But as shown in Fig. 9a the blue emission at 485 nm by CaCO₃ : La³⁺ after excitation at 365 nm, could be attributed to *n-π** transition from La³⁺²⁵. Whereas, CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ emitted green emission particularly at 545 nm on photo excitation at 365 nm⁻¹ (Fig. 9b) corresponding to the transition of ⁵D₄ → ⁷F₅ from Tb³⁺ ions.

Experimental

Materials :

All chemicals were of analytical grade and used without any further purification. CaCl₂·2H₂O was obtained from Merck. La(NO₃)₃·6H₂O, TbCl₃·6H₂O, pyrylene-3,4,9,10-tetra carboxylic dianhydride (PTCDA) dye were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich.

Synthesis of minerals :

Synthesis of hydrophobic calcium carbonate was carried out by taking 0.147 g (1.0 mM) of CaCl₂·2H₂O and different concentrations of lauric acid (0.01 mM, 0.02 mM and 0.1 mM) dissolved in 15 ml methanol in separate glass beakers. It was thoroughly stirred with the help of a magnetic stirrer. Each solution was then transferred

Table 1. Oil, toluene and xylene absorption efficiency of hydrophobic CaCO_3 , $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ and $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ samples in oil water mixture (1 : 10)^a

Sr. no.	Sample name	Name of oil or organic solvent	Wt. of recovered water (g)	Wt. of absorbed oil/ organic solvent (g)	Absorption efficiency (%)
1.	CaCO_3	Sunflower oil	4.4	0.46	100
2.	$\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$	Sunflower oil	4.3	0.32	69.5
3.	$\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$	Sunflower oil	4.3	0.30	35.2
4.	CaCO_3	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.4	0.31	70.5
5.	Ca-LaCO_3	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.2	0	21
6.	Ca-TbCO_3	<i>Ortho</i> xylene	4.3	0.22	50
7.	CaCO_3	Toluene	4.4	0.348	79.9
8.	$\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$	Toluene	4.4	0	23.5
9.	$\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$	Toluene	4.3	0.24	56

^aTotal volume of oil/organic solvent-water mixture was 5 mL; 0.5 g of $\text{CaCO}_3/\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}/\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ was added in each case.

Fig. 9. Photoluminescence spectrum of (a) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}$ (inset : optical microscopic picture of material under UV light), (b) $\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$ (inset : optical microscopic picture of material under UV light).

into petri dishes and covered with parafilm having 2 to 3 holes in it to allow carbon dioxide to enter into the solution via vapour diffusion. The parafilm covered petri dishes were then placed in a desiccator containing ammonium carbonate (CO_2 source). After 24 h, the crystals appeared in the petri dishes were filtered and washed several times with methanol. In case of rare-earth doped calcium carbonates, 0.147 g (1.0 mM) of $\text{CaCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ along with 0.4332 g (1.0 mM) $\text{La}(\text{NO}_3)_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ or 0.3734 g (1.0 mM) $\text{TbCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was used.

Absorption of oils and solvents :

Commercially available sunflower oil mixed with pyrylene-3,4,9,10-tetra-carboxylic dianhydride (PTCDA) dye was used for the oil absorption study. Mixture was prepared by adding 10 mg of PTCDA dye to oil and

water in 1 : 10 ratio. To this mixture 500 mg hydrophobic carbonate ($\text{CaCO}_3/\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{La}^{3+}/\text{CaCO}_3 : \text{Tb}^{3+}$) sample was added to test the absorption of oil.

Characterisation techniques :

The morphology of products was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) using FEI Quanta 200 FEG with EDS. Powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern was recorded on "PANALYTICAL X'Pertpro Powder X-ray diffractometer" with graphite monochromatic $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ ($\lambda = 1.5406 \text{ \AA}$) radiation at room temperature. Size of the calcium carbonate particles was measured by Dynamic Light Scattering technique (SZ100, Nanopartica, Horiba Scientific). The infrared spectrum was recorded using KBr pellet preparation method on a Perkin-Elmer "spectrum two FT-IR" system. Thermogravimetric Analy-

sis (TGA) was performed using “Melter Toledo TGA/DSC-1” apparatus in the temperature range between 25 and 800 °C under N₂ with a heating rate of 5 °C min⁻¹. Luminescence spectrum of solid sample was recorded with “Perkin-Elmer LS-55 Luminescence Spectrometer” at room temperature.

Conclusions

Synthesis of superhydrophobic CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ was investigated at room temperature in lauric acid medium. Especially, the morphology, absorption and optical properties were examined with influence of lauric acid and lanthanide dopants. After doping lanthanide elements into CaCO₃, spherical particles transformed to flower-like morphology.

The FT-IR spectra and thermogravimetric analysis (TGA) of the samples confirmed the presence of lauric acid on the surface of the synthesized carbonates. The water contact angle at 140° suggested the formation of superhydrophobic materials. CaCO₃, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ which displayed absorption of oil and genotoxic organic solvents such as xylene and toluene from an oil/organic solvent-water mixture. Further, CaCO₃ : La³⁺ exhibited blue luminescence and CaCO₃ : Tb³⁺ emitted green luminescence on photo excitation at 365 nm.

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